

Performance indicators of the technical and tactical actions of young football players of 13–14 years of various game roles

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Purpose: to determine the quality of the indicators of technical and tactical actions of young football players 13–14 years of different playing roles during the competitive activity.

Material & Methods: the study was conducted during a football competition. The study involved 11 football players 13–14 years of the football team Arsenal. The quality of the performance of technical and tactical actions was analyzed during 10 games in the championship competitions of the city of Kharkov in football. The analysis of literary sources, pedagogical observation and methods of mathematical statistics were used.

Results: the performance indicators for the technical and tactical actions of young football players 13–14 years during 10 games depending on the game role were determined.

Conclusions: the conducted studies show that the quality of the performance of technical and tactical actions among young football players 13–14 years old is not the same for players of different game roles. The results obtained indicate the need to determine model characteristics for players of each game role, compare them with existing ones, and develop special exercises to eliminate differences between them.

Keywords: quality of performance, technical and tactical actions, young football players, competitive activity.

Introduction

In solving the tasks of technical and tactical training of young football players, the continuity of the development and improvement of individual elements, the use of which is specific in the quantity and quality of the performance of technical and tactical actions, is not fully taken into account. Various scientific works have been devoted to various questions of the preparedness of young football players: physical training [1; 4; 10], technical training [4; 8; 11], accounting for game roles during training [12], training of young football players [6; 7] and others.

In the training of football players, two groups of exercises are used aimed at developing physical qualities: non-specific (running, jumping, exercises on power simulators) and specific (tactical and technical). Exercises of the first group contribute to the development of basic physical qualities (endurance and strength), while exercises of the second group turn these basic qualities into specific [3; 13].

The technical and tactical preparedness of young football players has always been in the field of vision of scientists and coaches [1; 3; 7]. At the same time, in the works of these authors the questions of the dependence of the level of technical and tactical preparedness of young football players on the level of special physical preparedness are not completely disclosed.

In scientific papers [1; 8], age-related volumes of performing technical and tactical actions of football players of different nature and conditions are given, as well as complexes of technical and tactical actions with a subsequent analysis of the consequences of the effectiveness of their implementation [4; 9].

In addition, football players who have the same level of technical and tactical preparedness can use different techniques and their connections in different ways, so it is very important to identify the level of creativity of football players of different game roles.

The quality of the performance of technical and tactical actions is the key to success in football, which allows you to control the game activity, contributes to the creation of scoring chances and ultimately win.

Thus, determining the quality of the performance of technical and tactical actions of football players of different roles and developing complex training tasks for further sports improvement determines the relevance of this study.

Purpose of the study: to determine the quality of the indicators of technical and tactical actions of young football players of 13–14 years of different playing roles during the competitive activity.

Material and Methods of the research

The study was conducted during a football competition, in which 11 football players 13–14 years old of the Arsenal football team took part. The quality of the performance of technical and tactical actions was analyzed during 10 games in the championship of the Kharkov football championship. The analysis of literary sources, pedagogical observation and methods of mathematical statistics were used.

Results of the research

The studies carried out during the annual macrocycle in order

to establish the quality indicators of the technical and tactical actions of young football players aged 13–14, during 10 games, indicate different qualitative indicators depending on the game role. It was found that the quality of their performance on average per game is (22,0%) (Table 1).

According to the results, central and extreme midfielders (23,7%, 23,8%) perform better quality of play, mainly due to short (32,1% and 31,6%) and medium (27,6% and 28,2%) of passes, dribbling (24,1% and 25,2%), tackles (34,0% and 20,1%), stopping the ball (25,8% and 30,2%) and kicks into the goal (26,0% and 32,0%).

In turn, central defenders have low performance in long passes (10,1%), groundmoves (15,1%) and tackles (16,0%).

The highest quality field players perform short and medium passes (31,9% and 26,0%), worse long passes, only 10,5% of them are high-quality.

At the same time, goalkeepers (37,1%) perform better short passes, which is due to the absence of predominantly counteraction to their implementation (Table 2), and worse – forwards (28,8%), since they are under close opposition.

The most difficult to accomplish are long ball passes, the quality of which is 10,5%, which are worse than other players by the attackers (9,1%), which is associated with technical and tactical actions that are not inherent to them (Table 2).

The average command indicator of the "stroke" is 14,8%, which for the attackers is positively performed in 20,1% of cases, significantly better than the wing back ($t=5,15$; $p<0,001$) and central ($t=4,62$; $p<0,001$) defenders and wing back ($t=5,61$; $p<0,001$) and central ($t=4,85$; $p<0,001$) midfielders (Table 3).

Field players equally possess the techniques of "dribbling

Table 1
Quality indicators of the performance of technical and tactical actions during the game of young football players 13–14 years of different game roles (according to the calculations of 10 games, %)

No. i/o	Technical and tactical actions	Playing roles						Total amount Σ , %	$\bar{X}$, %
		1 $\bar{X}_1 \pm m_1$	2 $\bar{X}_2 \pm m_2$	3 $\bar{X}_3 \pm m_3$	4 $\bar{X}_4 \pm m_4$	5 $\bar{X}_5 \pm m_5$	6 $\bar{X}_6 \pm m_6$		
1.	Short passes	37,1±2,03	31,2±1,24	30,8±1,22	32,1±1,24	31,6±1,30	28,8±1,28	191,4	31,9
2.	Medium passes	22,5±1,47	28,1±1,24	25,2±1,28	27,6±1,19	28,2±1,24	24,4±1,17	156,0	26,0
3.	Long passes	12,3±0,51	9,6±0,42	10,1±0,44	10,2±0,44	11,4±0,47	9,1±0,51	62,7	10,5
4.	Groundmoves	11,4±1,18	14,0±0,58	15,1±0,59	13,7±0,46	14,6±0,48	20,1±1,04	88,9	14,8
5.	Dribbling	20,3±1,05	26,2±1,03	25,8±1,17	24,1±1,17	25,2±1,19	24,8±1,02	146,4	24,4
6.	Slide tackle	–	30,0±1,58	16,0±1,26	34,0±1,59	20,1±1,21	15,0±1,19	115,1	23,0
7.	Ball stop	21,6±1,42	24,2±1,15	26,2±1,18	25,8±1,17	30,2±1,21	23,6±1,11	151,6	25,3
8.	Kicks to the goal	–	25,0±1,08	25,0±1,08	26,0±1,09	32,0±1,24	29,0±1,07	137,0	22,8
9.	Headshot	10,6±1,04	20,3±1,05	20,8±1,07	20,6±1,05	20,6±1,05	21,1±1,06	114,0	19,0
	Σ , %	135,8	208,6	195,0	214,1	213,9	195,9	1163,1	–
	X , %	19,4	23,2	21,7	23,8	23,7	21,8	–	22,3

Remark. 1 – goalkeepers (n=10); 2 – wing back defenders (n=20); 3 – central defenders (n=20); 4 – wing back midfielders (n=20); 5 – central midfielders (n=20); 6 – forwards (n=20).

Table 2

Matrix as indicators of the performance of "short", "medium" and "long" passes during the game by young football players of 13–14 years of different game roles (according to the calculations of 10 games, %)

No. i/o	Game roles	Motor actions	1	2	3	4	5	6
			1.	Goalkeepers (n=10)	a		2,48	2,66
		b		2,92	1,44	2,70	3,03	1,17
		c		4,09	3,28	3,13	0,43	4,44
2.	Wing back defenders (n=20)	a			1,51	0,27	0,05	2,16
		b			1,70	0,68	0,03	2,18
		c			0,82	0,98	2,86	0,81
3.	Central defenders (n=20)	a				1,43	1,75	0,87
		b				1,44	1,75	0,84
		c				0,11	2,03	1,52
4.	Wing back midfielders (n=20)	a					0,36	1,93
		b					0,76	1,79
		c					1,88	1,67
5.	Central midfielders (n=20)	a						1,53
		b						2,24
		c						3,19
6.	Forwards (n=20)	a						
		b						
		c						

Remark. a – short passes; b – medium passes; c – long passes.

the ball", the performance indicator of which is 24,1–26,2% ($p < 0,05$) (Table 3).

Performing "tackles" is one of the most complex element of football technique and is used by all field players, but their quality of execution is not the same. So, the most successful "tackles" are performed by wing back midfielders (34,0%) and wing back defenders (30,0%), which is significantly better than central defenders ($p < 0,05-0,001$) and attackers ($p < 0,01-0,001$) (Table 4).

"Stopping the ball" is used by all players, and its quality provides for the possibility of further implementation of technical and tactical actions. In our studies, the central midfielders (30,2%) most successfully stop the ball compared to goalkeepers ($t=4,62$; $p < 0,001$), wing back and central midfielders ($t=3,59$; $p < 0,01$; $t=2,37$; $p < 0,05$) and forwards ($t=2,62$; $p < 0,05$) (Table 4).

Higher quality exercise kicks into the goal (ie, get on goal) central midfielders (32,0%), which was significantly better than the wing back and central defenders ($t=4,27$; $p < 0,001$) and winger ($t=3,64$; $p < 0,01$) (Table 5).

The indicators of the positive performance of "head kicks" for both the player of his team and the goal kick for young field

players 13–14 years old do not have a significant difference ($p < 0,05$) and are in the range (20,3–21,1%).

Conclusions / Discussion

The technical and tactical preparedness of young football players has been considered in many scientific works [2; 8, etc.], in the works of which the issues of the dependence of the level of technical and tactical preparedness on the level of special physical fitness are disclosed to a certain extent. Along with this, it is very important to determine the influence of quantitative indicators on the implementation of technical and tactical actions, since the quality of their implementation is the key to success in football, which allows you to control game activity, helps to create goals and, ultimately, win. Therefore, the quality of the implementation of various technical and tactical actions by players of different game roles to a greater extent determines the success of the whole team [12].

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Table 3
Matrix as indicators of the performance of the "groundmoves" and "dribble" during the game by young football players of 13–14 years of different game roles (according to the calculation of 10 games, %)

No. i/o	Game roles	Motor actions	1	2	3	4	5	6
1.	Goalkeepers (n=10)	a		1,98	2,94	1,81	2,04	7,31
		b		4,04	3,50	2,39	3,36	2,87
2.	Wing back defenders (n=20)	a			1,33	0,41	0,80	5,13
		b			0,26	1,35	0,63	0,87
3.	Central defenders (n=20)	a				1,87	6,58	4,62
		b				1,02	0,45	0,63
4.	Wing back midfielders (n=20)	a					0,76	5,61
		b					0,66	0,42
5.	Central midfielders (n=20)	a						4,83
		b						0,24
6.	Forwards (n=20)	a						
		b						

Remark. a – tackles; b – dribble.

Table 5
Matrix as indicators of the performance of "kicks in the goal" and "head kicks" during the game by young football players 13-14 years of different game roles (according to the calculation of 10 games, %)

No. i/o	Game roles	Motor actions	1	2	3	4	5	6
1.	Goalkeepers (n=10)	a						
		b		6,55	6,85	6,71	6,68	7,05
2.	Wing back defenders (n=20)	a			0	0,65	4,27	2,63
		b			0,37	0,39	0,39	0,71
3.	Central defenders (n=20)	a				0,65	4,27	4,24
		b				0,28	0,28	0,31
4.	Wing back midfielders (n=20)	a					3,64	1,97
		b					0	0,42
5.	Central midfielders (n=20)	a						1,83
		b						0,39
6.	Forwards (n=20)	a						
		b						

Remark. a – kicks in the goal; b – head kicks.

Table 4

Matrix as indicators of the performance of "tackles" and "stopping the ball" during the game by young football players 13–14 years of different game roles (according to the calculation of 10 games, %)

No. i/o	Game roles	Motor actions	1	2	3	4	5	6
1.	Goalkeepers (n = 10)	a						
		b		1,42	2,49	2,26	4,62	1,11
2.	Wing back defenders (n = 20)	a			6,93	1,79	4,98	10,56
		b			1,21	0,98	3,59	0,38
3.	Central defenders (n = 20)	a				8,87	2,34	0,58
		b				0,24	2,37	1,61
4.	Wing back midfielders (n = 20)	a					6,95	9,55
		b					2,62	1,37
5.	Central midfielders (n = 20)	a						3,00
		b						4,02
6.	Forwards (n=20)	a						
		b						

Remark. a – tackles; b – stopping the ball.

technical and tactical actions, since the quality of their implementation is the key to success in football, which allows you to control game activity, helps to create goals and, ultimately, win. Therefore, the quality of the implementation of various technical and tactical actions by players of different game roles to a greater extent determines the success of the whole team (26,2%; 25,8%). Wing back midfielders were better at "tackling" (34,0%), short (32,1%) and medium (27,6%) passes. Central midfielders have the best indicators of their actions in the "stop" (30,2%) and kicking the ball (32,0%), short and medium passes (31,6%; 28,2%). The attackers to a greater extent of all technical and tactical actions qualitatively perform kicks into the goal (29,0%) and short passes of the

ball (28,8%).

Obtained results indicate the need to determine the normative (model) characteristics for players of each game role, comparing them with those available, and developing special exercises to resolve differences between them.

Prospects for further research. Prospects for further research include the establishment of a correlation dependence of the quality of the performance of technical and tactical actions on the number of motor actions of young players of different game roles.

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